

A Taxonomy of Externalization Policies

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Abstract

While we have witnessed a flurry of research on the history, politics, and legality of externalization policies, conceptual work has been relatively scarce. Against this backdrop, we put forward a taxonomy of externalization policies, distinguishing the spaces in which states aim to control human movements and limit their legal obligations towards people seeking protection as well as the means by which states exercise power. Essentially, states have strived to control territorial space through physical obstacles and digital innovation; legal space through policies of inadmissibility and practices of irresponsibility; diplomatic space through bilateral and multilateral cooperation; and influence mobility aspirations by targeting the mental space of potential migrants. The evolution of these four layers of refugee externalization implies supplementing biopolitics based on external migration control measures with transnational psychopolitics based on communicative strategies aiming to disincentivize departure by internalizing control.

Introduction

Refugee externalization policies have regained traction in many liberal Western democracies. Such policies intend to control human movement as well as to evade or, at least, reduce Western states' responsibility in refugee protection through territorial and legal externalization. Whereas *territorial externalization* aims to keep people seeking protection away from the territory of potential destination states, *legal externalization* aims to shift legal responsibility for refugees outside of the reach of the state's jurisdiction.¹ Despite policy innovation in the field of refugee externalization in recent years, the idea of circumventing state responsibility towards people seeking protection in this way is far from new with an intensified interest since the 1980s.²

While we have witnessed a flurry of research on the history, politics, and legality of externalization policies, conceptual work has been relatively scarce. Against this backdrop, we put forward a taxonomy that aims to capture the different forms of refugee externalization. We identify four layers of refugee externalization, differing by the spaces in which states strive to exercise control and the means by which states employ their power. First, states have aimed to control the *territorial space* preventing border-crossings of unwanted migrants by physical obstacles such as walls and fences or digital innovation and biometric databases. Second, states operate in the *legal space* when establishing procedural barriers or using their legislative power

to hinder people from accessing asylum procedures and refugee protection. Third, liberal democracies are increasingly using their international standing and asymmetric economic power in the *diplomatic space* to close agreements allowing them to outsource both migration control and refugee protection. Finally, states are disincentivizing the departure of people in main countries of origin and transit through media and peer campaigns, targeting mobility aspirations and the *mental space* of potential asylum seekers.

Rather than replacing each other, the different layers of externalization policies can be understood as overlapping dimensions of migration control that complement each other. Also in conjunction, these are not instruments leading to the full exclusion of people seeking protection but function as a series of filters inducing selection processes. Overall, we can observe an evolution from visible and direct state control measures to more sublime, indirect forms of state power that aim to establish mental barriers and manipulate mobility aspirations. This development implies supplementing *biopolitics*³, seeking to primarily control the movement of people at the hard edge of national borders in the Global North, with transnational *psychopolitics*⁴, focusing on the headspace of potential migrants in the Global South. At the same time, externalization policies have turned refugee policy from a matter of domestic affairs to a matter of foreign affairs, moving immigration control upwards to the intergovernmental sphere and outwards towards countries in closer proximity to humanitarian crises.⁵ Thereby, we witness a widening of the gap between what liberal democracies practice within their own borders and what they tolerate outside of their borders.⁶

Conceptualizing the externalization of refugee protection

Zolberg has been one of the researchers paving the way for research on externalization, describing practices such as the transatlantic visa system as a form of *remote control*.⁷ Repudiating an over-simplistic view of externalization policies as instruments that are denying access to national territory by tightening borders, Spijkerboer has developed the concept of a *global mobility infrastructure*.⁸ According to this conceptualization, the movement of people is regulated by physical structures, travel services, and laws, which are often discriminating along categories such as nationality, race, class, and gender. FitzGerald has categorizing externalization policies by using medieval metaphors – cages, domes, buffers, and barbicans – to describe the *architecture of repulsion* that states have erected to control the movement of unwanted migrants.⁹

Drawing on these and other studies, we put forward a taxonomy of refugee externalization focusing on the *spaces* in which states aim to regulate the movement and protection of migrants/refugees and the *means* by which states exercise power within these spaces. Distinguishing these two analytical dimensions allows to capture the various layers of refugee externalization, recognizing the growing influence of international cooperation and migration diplomacy as well as of more subtle means of control such as social media campaigns. On a subordinate level, we can also differentiate which authority exercises control, which type of power is employed, and via which instruments control is put into practice. The following table provides an overview of the four layers that constitute the taxonomy of externalization policies.

Table: Overview taxonomy of refugee externalization

Layer	National territory and digital technology	Asylum legislation and judicial application	Migration diplomacy and international cooperation	Mobility aspirations and migration narratives
<i>Dimension</i>				
<i>Space of influence</i>	Territorial space	Legal space	Diplomatic space	Mental space
<i>Aim of influence</i>	Hindering or deflecting human movement	Evading or obscuring legal responsibility	Shifting or outsourcing policy implementation	Preventing or minimizing mobility objectives
<i>Means of influence</i>	Direct influence via physical and digital infrastructure	Direct influence via legal infrastructure and administrative discretion	Indirect influence via foreign affairs and third countries	Indirect influence via media and international organizations
<i>Type of state power</i>	Compulsory power	Institutional power	Structural power	Productive power
<i>Instruments of externalization</i>	Fences, push-backs, detention facilities, visa restrictions, biometric databases, etc.	National asylum frameworks, unilateral safe third country policies, judicial discretion, etc.	Migration partnerships, readmission agreements / arrangements, regional consultative processes, etc.	Social media campaigns, performative cruelty, soap operas, peer-to-peer messaging, etc.

In the following sections, the different forms of refugee externalization are discussed in detail.

Controlling access to national territory

The first layer of externalization is reflected by the aim of states to control their territorial space using both physical and digital infrastructure to hinder unwanted migrants from accessing national territory. Rather than replacing physical border infrastructure the “digitalization of border control” has complemented it with extensive digital archives and transnational biometrical databases.¹⁰ Border control measures exercise *compulsory power* as they are based on states' direct application of coercive means.¹¹

Physical barriers, such as walls or fences, are seemingly medieval means but also the most visible representation of national borders. There are many examples of the continuous importance of such physical border infrastructure: the fences built around the Spanish enclaves Ceuta and Melilla after Spain joined the Schengen Agreement in 1991,¹² attempts by Poland to build a wall to secure the border against Belarus in 2022,¹³ or the fragmented yet growing border infrastructure at the US-Mexican border.¹⁴ Such border infrastructure is sometimes complemented with the use of physical force and the application of push-backs on land or with maritime interception. Such practices undermine the non-refoulement principle – the cornerstone of the international refugee regime. Meanwhile, reporting on the use of such practices has become notorious in Europe¹⁵ and overseas¹⁶.

Physical barriers go along with *paper walls*.¹⁷ The introduction of passports as well as entry and visa requirements that must be presented in departure countries is arguably the most common

tool used by states to this end.¹⁸ While visa requirements have been lifted in many Global North states over the past few decades, they are still a popular instrument to filter South-North movements, leading to a “global mobility divide”.¹⁹ In a similar way, states have introduced carrier sanctions on transportation companies should they not provide details about travelers and implement migration control measures.²⁰ What is more, states have also operated via a network of extraterritorial liaison officers that are translating mobility restrictions and operating as additional filters.²¹

Technological change has advanced digital infrastructures, turning physical obstacles into “smart borders”.²² Border patrols have been equipped with technical devices allowing them to scan fingerprints, irises, and facial characteristics.²³ These feed into extensive transnational biometric databases such as Eurodac and the Schengen Information System, storing information about the prior locations and asylum applications of people in EU and associated states. AI accelerates digital innovation and perpetuates control via robot dogs equipped with video cameras and sensors, operating alongside groups of automated ground vehicles²⁴ or networks of drones and automated surveillance towers.²⁵ While early accounts of digitization in border control and migration management have predicted that the border would likely lose some of its significance as a physical site,²⁶ the physical border infrastructure is not expected to lose importance any time soon.

Controlling access to asylum law

Besides controlling the access to national territory, states have also used different means to control the access to asylum law. By introducing unilateral policies of inadmissibility and using their discretionary power when interpreting laws, states control the legal space to evade protection responsibilities. Power unfolding via the (non-)use of laws and administrative discretion can be described as *institutional power* – it draws on formal and informal rules affecting individuals directly.²⁷

Most states worldwide have not only ratified international protection frameworks such as the 1951 Refugee Convention or the 1967 Protocol but also established national asylum frameworks.²⁸ They thereby formally recognize legal responsibility towards people seeking protection. From the 1980s onwards, states have subsequently limited this responsibility by introducing (safe) third country policies.²⁹ These policies allow states to deny access to refugee status determination and refugee protection based on a connection of an asylum applicant with another country.

Next to policies of inadmissibility, states have circumscribed their legal responsibility by interpreting existing laws in evasive ways. A particularly inventive move has been the exclusion of border or transit zones – such as airports, harbors, or coastlines – from state territory.³⁰ In doing so, states seek to avoid accountability and aim to evade fulfilling their obligations under human rights and refugee law. These zones enable states “to roll back human rights while leaving police powers in place” – or substantially increase them.³¹

Such policies allowing Western liberal states to exploit legal gaps whilst at the same time formally adhering to the principles of protection obligations have been coined as hyper-legalism and obfuscation.³² *Hyper-legalism* describes an overly formalistic bad-faith approach used by state officials when interpreting legal obligations towards people seeking protection. While

states are formally complying with the letter of international law, they are creating legal fiction and a level of formalistic sophistry that effectively undermines the spirit of international legal obligations. *Obfuscation*, in contrast, is based on secrecy about the actions that states are taking and the purported legal justifications. Using legal silence strategically, states strive to prevent legal accountability and reputational damage as they seek minimizing their responsibility in refugee protection.

Indirect control through migration diplomacy

Besides direct and unilateral measures frustrating access to their territory and asylum systems, states use also indirect means. Capitalizing on their economic power and international standing, Western states have increasingly engaged in what has been dubbed *migration diplomacy*.³³ This focuses on bilateral agreements with countries of transit and origin of migrants deflecting and deterring the latter and shifting legal obligations upon the former. In addition, informal inter-state consultation networks have proliferated in which states share “best practices” on asylum governance. Given that power is exercised indirectly and on the basis of economic predominance, these agreements can be interpreted as an example of *structural power*.³⁴

The evolution of readmission agreements is arguably the clearest expression of intensifying migration diplomacy. Facing a “deportation gap”³⁵ states have increasingly sought to close bilateral agreements with main states of origin and transit to return irregular migrants. From 2004 onwards, also the EU has negotiated a series of multilateral readmission agreements.³⁶ In return, target states have often been offered visa facilitation agreements.³⁷ However, the conclusion of formal agreements often faces opposition in the target states and even once concluded agreements have proved ineffective.³⁸ In result, states have turned towards informal cooperation on return and readmission.³⁹ Western states have also tried to capitalize on issue-linkages, connecting demands for readmission with incentives in trade, security, human rights, and development cooperation.⁴⁰

Particularly informal bilateral cooperation such as migration partnerships or memoranda of understanding focuses not only on the return of third-country nationals but also seeks to prevent the arrival of unwanted migrants. While the informalization may have motivated some transit and origin states to enter in such arrangements, destination states can also use informalization as a means for “breaking the legal link” with their own jurisdiction.⁴¹ In response, human rights lawyers have increasingly filed complaints to international courts such as the International Criminal Court to “break the cycle of impunity”.⁴²

Another form of migration diplomacy consists in agreements that shift responsibility for asylum processing and, in some cases, refugee protection to another country. Such (*safe*) *fourth country policies* date back to the 1980s and have, until the time of writing, been put into practice by Australia, Israel, and the United States.⁴³ Despite their continuous failure in the face of legal and practical challenges as well as human rights violations, they have an enduring appeal for politicians of Western states.⁴⁴ While Denmark was the first European state to introduce a legislative amendment allowing for such international agreements, it is the United Kingdom that has concluded the first such agreement with Rwanda in 2022, followed by Italy with Albania in 2024. This externalization follows the example of Australia's “Pacific Solution”, which itself took

inspiration from the offshoring of asylum processing by the United States in Guantanamo Bay, Cuba.⁴⁵ But while these agreements essentially aim at deterring asylum seekers from seeking asylum in the West, they often been framed as humanitarian projects by their defenders.⁴⁶

Controlling mobility aspirations

The fourth layer of externalization consists neither in territorial nor in legal or in diplomatic means to preclude access to Western states asylum systems. In contrast, it targets the ambition to migrate in the first place. Addressing the narratives of migration, this more subtle form of externalization refrains from the open use of force and instead operates via concealed and indirect ideational mechanisms masked as neutral “information campaigns”. Such influence conforms with the notion of *productive power*.⁴⁷ It mirrors the attempt to overcome the *biopolitics* that characterizes other forms of refugee externalization aiming to control the body and movement of potential migrants.⁴⁸ Due to its sublime and permissive nature and because it targets the mental space of people rather than their body it can best be described as a form of transnational *psychopolitics*.⁴⁹

The past decades have witnessed a proliferation of so-called “information campaigns” that essentially aim to disincentivize potential asylum seekers from moving by disseminating reports about risks on the journey and in destination countries. The Australian government, for example, has built up an extensive social media campaign disseminating the message to people without valid visa: “You will never set foot in Australia”.⁵⁰ While other states have chosen different channels of communication and more subtle ways of communication they are often built upon the principle of “negative nation branding”.⁵¹ Despite that research gives little support to the deterrent effects of such campaigns, their popularity is growing.⁵² Part of destination states' strategy is to send such messages indirectly via seemingly “neutral” international organizations like IOM, which are using, among other means, via peer-to-peer messaging such as the “migrants as messengers” project based on which returnees shall disincentivize the departure of their fellow citizens.⁵³

Next to deterrent information campaigns, Western states also make use of symbolic or *performative cruelty* to discourage people from moving. While the emergence of illiberal policies and practices is often attributed to right-wing parties, also mainstream parties play their role using accommodative strategies.⁵⁴ At the same time as they establish hostile environments wealthy destination states collaborate to set up *safe zones* in the region of main refugee countries.⁵⁵ Yet both the hostile environments in destination states and presumably safe zones in the region of origin ultimately aim to keep people seeking protection away from potential destination states in the Global North, simultaneously using and strengthening *regimes of (im)mobility*.⁵⁶

Conclusion

This contribution has put forward a novel taxonomy of refugee externalization policies. It shows that refugee externalization has many layers and that states are using their influence in

territorial, legal, diplomatic, and mental space to limit human mobility and their protection obligations.

The focus on illiberal externalization policies by Western democracies does not imply that states in the Global South have refrained from adopting similar strategies to imitate irresponsibility in refugee protection. For example, states in the Global South are also limiting the movement of South-South migration using visa policies.⁵⁷ Likewise, (safe) third country policies have increasingly become popular beyond the Global North.⁵⁸ However, states in the Global South are also using different means such as *strategic non-regulation* to avoid recognizing legal responsibility toward refugees.⁵⁹ Finally, they have also used instruments such as diaspora and emigration politics to yield influence in Western destination states.⁶⁰ What is more, refugee externalization is not only driven by states but can also be advanced by non-state actors such as international organizations.

Hitherto, liberal democracies have been cautious not to openly refrain from their commitment under the 1951 Refugee Convention. They may do so not only to prevent reputational damage but also because reducing their responsibility toward people seeking protection only works if the latter find protection elsewhere. However, extending responsibility to other countries and actors cannot work without maintaining responsibility in liberal democracies. When Western states undermine liberal protection norms within and beyond their borders, they erode the very substance of the international refugee regime. Doing so by exploring legal grey zones or even openly announcing to pull out from international courts, not only affects people seeking protection but also the very foundations on which the liberal international order rests.⁶¹

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